

FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONALLY IMPORTANT FEATURES OF ATTENTION IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. This article raises the issue of the importance of the targeted formation of the characteristics of mental processes that ensure the effectiveness of performing professional tasks in future specialists. Based on a comparative analysis of the content of the training process of highly qualified athletes and the physical education of students, the need to implement special exercises that contribute to the targeted formation of professionally important features of attention is substantiated.

Keywords. Psycho-physical, social training, attention development, physical training, physical education of students.

OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARI TALABALARI JISMONIY TARBIYASIDA E'TIBORNING KASBIY MUHIM XUSUSIYATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak mutaxassislarda kasbiy vazifalarni bajarish samaradorligini ta'minlovchi ruhiy, ijtimoiy jarayonlarning xususiyatlarini maqsadli shakllantirish muhimligi masalasi ko'tarilgan. Yuqori malakali sportchilarning o'quv-mashg'ulot jarayoni va talabalarning jismoniy tarbiyasi mazmunini qiyosiy tahlil qilish asosida diqqatning kasbiy muhim xususiyatlarini maqsadli shakllantirishga yordam beradigan maxsus mashqlarni amalga oshirish zarurati asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar. Ruhiiy-jismoniy, ijtimoiy tayyorgarlik, diqqatni rivojlantirish, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, o'quvchilarni jismoniy tarbiyalash.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО ВАЖНЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ВНИМАНИЯ В ФИЗИЧЕСКОМ ВОСПИТАНИИ СТУДЕНТОВ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье поднимается вопрос о важности целенаправленного формирования особенностей психических, социальных процессов, обеспечивающих эффективность выполнения профессиональных задач у будущих специалистов. На основе сравнительного анализа учебно-тренировочного процесса высококвалифицированных спортсменов и содержания физического воспитания студентов обоснована необходимость внедрения специальных упражнений, способствующих целенаправленному формированию профессионально важных характеристик внимания.

Ключевые слова. Психофизическая, социальная подготовка, развитие внимания, физическая подготовка, физическое воспитание учащихся.

Relevance. Socio-economic changes in society require an increase in the requirements for the level of comprehensive training of future specialists to perform professional tasks. Analysis of the working programs of students of higher educational institutions on physical education shows that one of the tasks of physical education is the formation of psychophysical readiness for professional activity. While not denying the importance of this task, it should be noted that working programs usually do not provide a set of means to achieve this state. Some contradictions are observed between the goals and objectives of physical education outlined in the explanatory notes of the programs and the content of the practical and control sections. In this regard, the problem of searching for means of forming the psychological and physical readiness of students of higher educational institutions for professional activity is relevant. In addition, according to the conducted research [4], the content of this type of training, among other factors, includes the characteristics of various neuropsychic processes (attention, thinking, memory, etc.), which determine the effectiveness of the performed activity.

The purpose of the research is to reveal the content of physical education that ensures the formation of the characteristics of neuropsychic processes that ensure the productivity of future professional activity in students.

Research objectives: 1) comparative analysis of the level of formation of attention characteristics and physical fitness of the subjects in different content of physical education; 2) development of practical recommendations for the selection of the content of physical education of students, ensuring the targeted formation of attention characteristics that determine the effectiveness of professional and social activity.

Purpose of the study: To solve the research objective, the following methods were used: analysis of scientific and methodological literature; generalization of the obtained data; pedagogical observation; formative experiment and methods of mathematical statistics. The reliability of the obtained results was determined based on Student's t-test. Psychological tests characterizing the manifestation of attention selectivity (according to the Münsterberg method) and its concentration (according to the Perron-Ruser test) served as a diagnostic tool for determining the characteristics of attention that determine the effectiveness of educational and professional activity [6]. For ease of receiving test results, its indicators were determined as a percentage of the maximum possible result in each test.

Experimental work was conducted with students of the Faculty of Natural Sciences of the Karakalpak State University. 39 first-year female students participated in the experiment. The content of physical education of the subjects included exercises for the development of attention characteristics (transfer, distribution, and stability), performed after the introductory part of the lesson. As these exercises, 11 modified Schulte tables consisting of random placements of digits

from 1 to 25 were used, in each of which the digits are reflected in plain writing and in a mirror relative to the horizontal and vertical axes. The level of physical fitness of the subjects was determined by the indicators of general endurance according to the results of the control test in the 1500m run.

Experimental work was carried out from September 2025 to the end of January 2026. During the experiment, 28 training sessions were conducted.

Research results and their discussion. As is known from the results of previous studies [1,5], increasing the functional capabilities of the body contributes to an increase in the effectiveness of neuropsychic processes. This condition is explained by the physiological unity of the fatigue onset mechanism (physical, mental, emotional, and sensory). This manifests as a disruption of the balance of inhibition processes in the central nervous system and occurs due to a decrease in the body's oxygen capacity during the performance of activities [2]. However, the data obtained by us, presented in Table 1, show that a relative increase in the aerobic productivity of the female student body does not automatically lead to an increase in the productivity of neuropsychic processes. Thus, if during the experiment in the 1500-meter run, the indicators in the control exercise changed significantly ($P < 0.05$), then the indicators of attention selectivity did not change significantly ($P > 0.05$). At the same time, a sufficiently reliably confirmed negative dynamic was revealed in the indicators of attention concentration. In our opinion, this can be explained by the fact that female students regularly perform aerobic exercises in the process of physical education, which leads to an increase in the indicators of the 1500-meter run control exercise, and exercises aimed at forming concentration are not provided for in the content of working programs on physical education. Accordingly, due to the dialectical nature of phenomena of various natures [6], in the absence of progressive processes, regressive processes begin to prevail.

Table 1

Ratio of initial and final indicators of the experimental participants, $M \pm m$

Trials	Initial	Final	P_1	Shifting
Focus selectivity, % of maximum	44,62±2,98	48,72±2,05	>0,05	4,1
Focus, maximum %	80,59±1,6	72,16±3,19	<0,05	8,43
1500 m run, s	732,71±11,51	701,45±9,16	<0,05	31,26

A slight increase in attention selectivity indicators is explained by the fact that female students performed exercises to develop it in the final part of the warm-up, but the insufficient duration of the experiment did not allow achieving significant results. The obtained experimental data, in our opinion, do not contradict the results of the conducted preliminary studies, according to which the nature of sports activity leads to an increase in the level of formation of features of neuropsychic processes that determine its effectiveness [1,3,4,5]. In the conducted experiments, highly qualified athletes were considered as subjects, whose training process is characterized by a high level of intensity, which indirectly leads to significant changes in the studied indicators. For students, obtaining a final grade for physical education classes is the

leading motive, which does not contribute to increasing the intensity of training sessions. Moreover, the constant increase in the number of students allocated to special medical groups and therapeutic physical education based on their health status does not allow for the implementation of existing sports training methods in the practice of physical education in higher educational institutions.

Conclusion. The results of the conducted experiment show that a slight increase in the aerobic productivity of the student body does not automatically lead to an increase in the productivity of the course of neuropsychic processes. At the same time, in order to fully achieve the goals of physical education, which provide for the formation of psychophysical readiness of students for professional activity, it is necessary to develop and implement special tasks that contribute to a targeted increase in the level of formation of the characteristics of neuropsychic processes that determine the effectiveness of professional and social activity in the practice of their physical education. The significance of this is determined, firstly, by the constantly growing scientific nature of modern production, which implies a high level of readiness to solve intellectual problems.

Adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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